

TEAMWORK TRIUMPHS: FOSTERING STUDENT DEVELOPMENT THROUGH COOPERATIVE LEARNING IN UNIVERSITY PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: *Cooperative learning is a pedagogical approach widely applied in various educational contexts, with particular relevance in the domain of physical education. This approach's practical value in physical education has gained significant recognition. College and university-level physical education instruction aims to enhance students' physical fitness, stimulate their intrinsic motivation for participating in physical activities, and thereby promote their holistic development and well-being. However, several challenges persist in the effective application of cooperative learning within the realm of college physical education instruction. Enhancing the quality of physical education teaching and refining the utilization of cooperative learning pedagogy has emerged as a pivotal concern for physical education educators in higher education.*

Keywords: *cooperative learning, physical education, college, pedagogical approach, student development*

1. Introduction

The educational model of cooperative learning has been widely used, especially in physical education teaching, the practical value of cooperative learning as an educational model has been highlighted. Physical education teaching in colleges and universities should improve the physical quality of students, guide students to develop a sense of initiative to participate in sports activities, and then promote students' healthy growth and all-round development. However, there are certain problems in the application of cooperative learning in college physical education teaching, how to improve the quality of college physical education teaching, improve the application of cooperative learning education mode, has become a key topic that college physical education teachers need to solve.

2. Problems in the application of cooperative learning in the teaching of physical education in colleges and universities

2.1. Students are not highly motivated

Physical education teaching courses in colleges and universities are often based on elective courses, due to the limitation of the number of physical education courses, some students are not able to take their

favourite physical education courses. In this context, the enthusiasm and initiative of students to participate in sports teaching activities are greatly reduced. At the same time, students in college physical education classes come from different classes and different majors. When carrying out sports cooperative learning, due to the unfamiliarity between students, resulting in the process of cooperation will often be reluctant to share communication or interpersonal conflicts and other issues, students and students and students and teachers have not established a close relationship of mutual help, which in turn affects the enthusiasm of students to participate in cooperative learning.

2.2. Students have a weak sense of co-operation

Due to the high autonomy of students in the college sports classroom, when teachers adopt cooperative learning, students tend to combine with their good friends or prefer to cooperate with students with higher levels of sports. This leads to a large difference in the level of sports skills between groups, so that students can not get the expected results of sports teaching after participating in sports training. The main reason for this phenomenon is that students are more self-conscious and lack the awareness of sharing and cooperative learning. Therefore, when teachers apply the teaching mode of co-operative learning in the sports classroom, they should follow the grouping principle of heterogeneity within groups and homogeneity among groups to ensure that the level of the groups is comparable to each other. Through the implementation of varied sports activities, students can form closer bonds and develop a sense of mutual support and collaboration, consequently enhancing the quality of cooperative learning [1].

2.3. Teachers' teaching role has not changed

The application of cooperative learning in college physical education requires that students be the centre of the physical education classroom and that students' subjective initiative be brought into play. This requires teachers to change their teaching concepts and roles in college sports teaching. However, at present, most college physical education teachers do not really recognise the role of teachers in the cooperative learning teaching mode, and still use the traditional teaching methods to make students passive in physical education learning. Therefore, teachers should change their teaching roles in the cooperative learning mode in a timely manner, and assume the roles of organisers, instructors and evaluators of physical education teaching activities, so that students can become the protagonists of the physical education classroom.

3. The path to improve the quality of co-operative learning in sports teaching in colleges and universities

3.1. Clear sports co-operative learning objectives

In the application of cooperative teaching mode in college sports teaching, teachers should clarify the learning objectives of cooperative learning, to carry out cooperative learning content and cooperative teaching links to guide the direction. At the same time, by clarifying the educational objectives of co-

operative learning, students can also be guided to take the initiative to solve the problems encountered in sports learning, so as to alleviate the fear of students in colleges and universities to participate in sports teaching activities. In the application of cooperative learning teaching mode in college sports teaching, from the students to participate in sports teaching self-confidence and self-esteem, to develop a level of teaching objectives. Therefore, college physical education teachers should have a detailed understanding of students' physical fitness and sports level before formulating the teaching objectives of co-operative learning, not only to give full play to the personal value of college students, but also to enable students to make progress in the process of co-operation.

For example, when teaching three-step layup in basketball class, teachers should make clear the teaching objectives of this lesson. Firstly, students should understand the basic points of three-step layup and master the basic skills of three-step layup through this lesson. Secondly, in order to make students understand that basketball is a group sport, teachers should guide students to practice the basic skills of three-step layup through cooperative learning, and form a sense of co-operation, competition, solidarity and collective honour in the process of applying the skills. After clarifying the teaching objectives of co-operative learning, teachers should group the students into groups according to their actual learning situation and ability in this lesson, and evenly distribute the students with higher, medium and lower levels of three-step layup skills to avoid the phenomenon of large differences in the level between groups, enhance the fairness of co-operative learning in basketball, and contribute to the cultivation of the spirit of basketball among the students. At the same time, it can also make students in the process of group-to-group confrontation, stimulate the fun of competition, enhance the students' competitive level and competitive awareness. Before the formal start of basketball three-step layup teaching, teachers should make students understand that this class is to carry out co-operative competitive confrontation activities to stimulate students' interest in learning and the spirit of victory, under the role of the spirit of victory, students tend to carry out more serious learning, improve students' motivation to learn, but also to ensure the quality of teaching [2].

3.2. Selection of co-operative learning mode

To improve the effectiveness of physical education teaching in colleges and universities, it is crucial to select an appropriate cooperative learning mode based on the physical education teaching content and objectives. Modes such as peer cooperation, group cooperation, and full cooperation can be considered. Furthermore, optimizing the organizational design of cooperative physical education learning should be prioritized.

First, peer cooperation mode. Peer cooperation mode is a commonly used form of cooperative learning organization in college sports teaching, and compared with other cooperative learning modes, peer cooperation mode is easier and freer to organize. Peer co-operation mode is mostly composed of good friends, due to the high degree of tacit understanding between good friends, so the application of peer

co-operation mode in college sports teaching can enhance the teaching effect. For example, in the college sports broadcast gymnastics teaching, the teacher in teaching abdominal and back movement, by the students of the teacher taught the movement to learn and imitate. After the completion of the study by the students to choose their own learning partners to carry out peer co-operation, learning in the process of peer co-operative learning, students correct each other's mistakes, and finally show the results of learning together. As the peer cooperative learning mode with the tacit understanding and intimate relationship between friends, not only can students enhance the interest of sports learning, but also can encourage each other, supervise each other, improve the effect of sports learning, but also can make the students in the process of peer cooperative learning to develop the good quality of learning from each other.

Second, group cooperation mode. Group co-operation mode is often used in the form of high school sports teaching in large classes, how to improve the quality of group co-operative learning, the teacher should be scientific grouping of group members. In order to carry out scientific and effective sports learning grouping, teachers should choose the appropriate grouping scheme according to the actual sports teaching content. One is to stabilize the grouping pattern. For example, in physical training, teachers can group students according to their gender, physical fitness level and previous physical fitness test scores. For example, boys with higher physical fitness levels are divided into a group, and those with poorer physical fitness levels are divided into a group, and such grouping patterns are used as the learning unit of physical education in this semester. This grouping mode makes the physical fitness level of the students in the group, there is not a big difference, but their interest in sports learning and sports skills but there is a certain difference, through such a group grouping mode can be realised according to the ability to teach. The second is the stage grouping mode. Stage grouping mode refers to the stage of group maintenance, teachers can complete a teaching unit after the dissolution or reorganization of the group. Stage grouping mode is more suitable for more targeted sports teaching content, so teachers can be based on sports teaching content and sports teaching objectives for students to stage grouping. For example, when teaching swimming in colleges and universities, teachers can test students' swimming level and swimming ability, and divide them into groups that can swim and groups that are beginners. After the completion of the group division, the two groups to implement different teaching strategies and teaching methods, the implementation of differentiated teaching and stratified teaching, not only can promote the growth and development of students, but also can improve the teaching effect of swimming [3].

Thirdly, full cooperation mode. Full cooperation mode refers to the teachers and students in high school sports teaching to build a cooperative relationship, when students learn sports knowledge or sports skills, through the teacher's guidance and help, to improve the students' comprehensive ability, this kind of co-operative learning mode is mainly used in the more difficult sports teaching.

3.3. Determine the form of cooperative learning

In high school sports teaching, group cooperative learning, group cooperative competition, group cooperative realization is to carry out a variety of forms of cooperative learning teaching mode, teachers can choose the appropriate form of learning based on the content of teaching and students' sports level. First, group cooperative learning. Group co-operative learning requires students to improve the technical level of sports in the form of a group, in the application of group co-operative learning form, the teacher should be based on the content of each group, the practice of different content, to develop different learning rules, and by the group responsible for the implementation of the learning rules and unified training. In the process of group co-operative learning, the group responsible person can supervise the students' sports training, and correct and change the students' problems in time.^[4]

Second, group cooperation competition. Competition teaching mode is the key link in the college sports teaching to effectively improve students' sports skills and test students' sports level, by carrying out group cooperation competition, organizing students to carry out sports confrontation in small groups. Teachers should carry out specific planning for the content of group co-operation competitions, and the person in charge of the group uniformly leads the students to carry out intra-group competitions or inter-group competitions. After the group completes the intra-group competition, the excellent group representatives are selected to carry out inter-group competition with other groups, and the teacher and other students evaluate the process and results of the competition and select the best athletes. In this process, the teacher should carefully observe each student's sports skills application points, and timely technical guidance.

Thirdly, the form of group co-operation practice. The application of sports skills, the practice of sports skills and sports drills are all sports practice activities. Through the group cooperation practice, students are grouped and issued with learning tasks, and students practice the learning tasks in groups and summarise the problems arising in the process of practice, which can be solved by the group cooperation or consulting the teacher. In the process of group co-operation and practice, it can stimulate the students' innovative consciousness and co-operation spirit, and improve their sense of responsibility. After completing the learning task, the group will carry out the exercise and the teacher will evaluate it, so as to promote the improvement of students' comprehensive quality.^[5]

3.4. Improve the evaluation content of cooperative learning

Cooperative learning in college sports teaching should take students as the centre of sports teaching classroom, at the same time, the teaching evaluation of cooperative learning also affects the quality of students' cooperative learning and sports teaching effect. Therefore, by improving the evaluation content of cooperative learning to promote the complementarity of strengths between students and the value of play, can effectively stimulate students' interest in learning and ability to improve.^[6]

First, teachers should comprehensively grasp the progress of group cooperative learning. For example, through frequent movement and careful observation, teachers in the sports classroom are able to understand the learning process of each group and identify any issues. They can then provide timely feedback and correction to enhance students' cooperative thinking. During the evaluation process, teachers rely on their observations of the group cooperative learning to assess the progress. To encourage self-improvement, teachers combine criticism and praise to guide students in recognizing their weaknesses and leveraging their strengths. These practices aim to boost students' self-confidence and increase their participation in sports teaching. [7]

Secondly, with the help of multiple evaluation system, students are evaluated comprehensively, changing the traditional evaluation method which is mainly based on learning achievements, and making awards such as the best co-operation award and sportsmanship award as one of the contents of teaching evaluation, which can stimulate students to participate in physical education teaching and learning activities, and at the same time can also affirm students' learning achievements.

4. Conclusion

In the context of the continuous promotion of educational reform, college physical education teachers should pay attention to the application and exploration of cooperative learning as an educational model, start from a new perspective, give full play to the value of cooperative learning teaching methods, make clear the educational objectives of cooperative learning in physical education teaching, and choose the appropriate cooperative learning mode and cooperative learning form according to the actual situation of students and the content of physical education teaching, so that students can improve their ability to learn independently and cooperative awareness in physical education teaching. Independent learning ability and cooperative consciousness, at the same time, teachers should pay attention to the evaluation of cooperative learning, so as to enhance students' learning enthusiasm and learning ability, to ensure the effect of physical education teaching.

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